

Interactive technologies as a method of improving the modern teaching of English

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Annotation. The article is focused on the research and development of interactive methodological approaches in the training of future military specialists during English language classes. It is noted that the methodology in the English language teaching system comprehensively takes into account the peculiarities and mechanisms of developing communicative skills among students according to the defined programme goals and objectives. Since technology has evolved in various industries, the education sector has also started using technological tools to improve learner achievement. With the right tools, it has become easy to engage learners in tasks by allowing them to do this in a multimedia way.

It is emphasised that the task of education is primarily to develop a person's readiness to realise his/her personal and professional potential in the new changing conditions. It is highlighted that special attention should be paid to the most effective teaching methods - interactive methods which allow students to gain experience of actively controlled communication, learn to express and stand up for their own opinions, and show their individuality.

All of the aforementioned is in line with the priorities of communication and interactivity. Rapid social development of a country is impossible apart from the development of the creative and moral potential of its citizens, and without their activity, initiative and abilities. Formation of these and other qualities is known to take place during the period of study, so the most important task of an educational institution is to form the personality of students, to create conditions that ensure the development of their individuality and creative abilities.

The author concludes that the unique and exceptional value of interactive methods of teaching English lies in the fact that students learn to work effectively in a team and optimise the learning process. Perspective directions for further research are the search for innovative methods of teaching activities that can teach students to think critically and solve complex problems by analysing circumstances and relevant information.

Keywords: interactive technologies, cooperative learning, multimedia, brainstorming, group work, project method, critical thinking.

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Інтерактивні технології як засіб удосконалення сучасного заняття з англійської мови

Анотація. Статтю присвячено дослідженню і розробці інтерактивних методичних підходів під час підготовки майбутніх військових фахівців на занятті з англійської мови. Зауважено, що методологія в системі навчання англійської мови комплексно враховує особливості і механізми розвитку комунікативних навичок у здобувачів освіти за визначеними програмними цілями та завданнями. З розвитком технологій у різних галузях, освітня галузь також почала використовувати технологічні інструменти для покращення результатів слухачів. Завдяки правильним інструментам стало легко залучати слухачів до виконання завдань, дозволяючи їм робити це в мультимедійному вигляді.

Наголошено на тому, що завдання освіти полягає насамперед у розвитку готовності людини реалізувати свій особистий і професійний потенціал у нових мінливих умовах. Підкреслено, що особливої уваги потребують методи навчання, які є найбільш ефективними, – інтерактивні методи, що дають змогу слухачам набувати досвіду активно-контрольованого спілкування, вчитися висловлювати й відстоювати власну думку, проявляти індивідуальність.

Вищезазначене суголосне з пріоритетами, якими є комунікативність та інтерактивність. Інтенсивний соціальний розвиток країни неможливий без розвитку творчого і морального потенціалу її громадян, без їх активності, ініціативи, здібностей. Формування цих та інших якостей відбувається, як відомо, в період навчання, тому найважливішим завданням освітнього закладу є формування особистості слухачів, створення умов, що забезпечують розвиток їх індивідуальності, творчих здібностей.

Автором зроблено висновок, що своєрідна та виняткова цінність інтерактивних методів навчання англійській мові полягає в тому, що слухачі навчаються ефективній роботі в колективі, оптимізації навчального процесу. Перспективними напрямками подальших досліджень є пошук інноваційних методів навчальної діяльності, за допомогою яких можна навчити слухачів критично мислити, розв'язувати складні проблеми шляхом аналізу обставин і відповідної інформації.

Ключові слова: інтерактивні технології, кооперативне навчання, мультимедійні засоби, мозковий штурм, робота в групі, метод проектів, критичне мислення.

Introduction

The actual problems of improving classes related to the forms of organising students' educational activities involve, first of all, activating the role of the student, transforming him or her from an object of learning into its subject using the methods of personality-oriented learning. An integral component of the foreign language study programme is the development of students' creative potential and the formation of creative activity experience, which is the most important task of contemporary higher education [12, 75]. The ability to perform creative tasks of different levels (theoretical, practical, problematic, educational and research) is a prerequisite for acquiring new knowledge and intellectual development of the individual.

The professional development of students' creative potential consists of achieving a positive level of learning and gaining experience of artistic activity. The creative level of learning is achieved by introducing into the educational process technologies of consistent and gradual assimilation of knowledge by students at the reproductive, reproductive-productive and creative levels [2, 38]. At the I-II reproductive levels, students develop skills and abilities of executive work, at the III reproductive-productive level they acquire skills and capabilities that are necessary for solving various professional problems, and at the IV

creative level they acquire skills and knowledge of creative work. Consistent four-level training will enable the student to realise themselves in the future as a person who can combine executive, managerial and creative work.

The didactic aspect of the use of interactive technologies is studied by such well-known scientists as G.M. Bros, A. Gin [4, 7-11], M.V. Claren, L.V. Pirozhenko [8], N.F. Fomin, O.I. Pometun [13, 2-6], N. Suvorova and others. In particular, L.V. Pirozhenko and O.I. Pometun [15] proposed a conditional classification of interactive technologies by forms of learning (models) in which interactive methods are implemented.

Despite numerous works on this topic, some issues remain unexplored: scholars cannot reach a consensus on the role of interactive technologies in English language classes. The relevance of the article is stipulated by the urgent need to improve the modern English language class in higher education, so it is very important for an educator to master new methods on a creative level in order to achieve the interconnection of educational, developmental and motivational components of learning activities in a single lesson and in the system of lessons, to establish humane relationships in the team, and to actively use different forms of cooperation with students [1, 52].

The objective of the article is to define the basic principles and innovative means of improving English classes at the present stage, to study the possibility of increasing the effectiveness of using interactive teaching methods in the process of forming communicative competence.

Results

The problem of human adaptation in modern society is quite relevant. This is due to changes in the external natural and social environment, human activity, the formation of new social relations, and the entry of society into a new (information) phase of its development. In this situation, the task of education is primarily to develop a person's readiness to realise his or her personal and professional potential in the new changing conditions. Therefore, we need a system of education that can teach a person to adapt to the conditions of life and work [18, 2]. To do this, a person has to accept and assimilate new knowledge of different levels and orientations, develop the essential skills and abilities, and apply them in professional and personal activities.

Particular attention should be paid to the most effective teaching methods - interactive methods that allow students to gain experience in actively controlled communication, learn to express and defend their own opinions, and show their individuality.

In modern didactics, there are four forms of organising educational activities within the framework of a class: interaction between a teacher and a student or a student and a student (pair); simultaneous teaching of the whole group by a teacher (group); activation of all students who teach each other (collective); independent work of students (individual)[6, 7].

According to the participation of students in educational activities, three learning models can be distinguished, which imply a certain level of cognitive activity: low level - reproductive activity, when the student shows little or no independence and creativity (passive model); medium level - the student performs creative tasks, enters into a dialogue with the teacher (active model); higher level - constant, active interaction of all students.

What teaching methods are typical for these models? In the first case, the student acts as an object of learning and resembles a vessel that needs to be filled with information, the sources of knowledge are the teacher, textbook, etc. Students usually do not communicate with each other, do not perform any creative tasks, but only assimilate and reproduce the material presented [9, 5]. Teaching methods in this model include a monologue lecture, reading, explanation, demonstration, and reproductive questioning of students. At their best, these methods ensure up to 30% of information is absorbed.

In the active model, teaching methods stimulate students' cognitive activity and independence, such as problem and creative tasks, independent work, questions from students to teachers and vice versa, which develop creative thinking [3, 57]. The active model involves differentiating learning by individualising programmes and tasks. The level of knowledge assimilation is quite high, but since students do not interact, some of them may be outside the learning process. In addition, the teacher's workload is quite high.

In contrast to the models discussed above, interactive technology training develops students' ability to transfer the acquired skills and ways of doing things to different subjects and everyday life, and forms social and civic competence. The level of knowledge is quite high, but the learning outcomes are less predictable and require further correction. The teacher acts as an organiser and consultant, ensuring a democratic, equal partnership between himself/herself and the students. In the process of learning, students make important decisions, have the opportunity to communicate, and are involved in various activities that arouse interest in learning and provide deep internal motivation [19].

All kinds of methods and technologies are important for learning. For interactive technologies, the so-called passive methods are an integral element. Depending on the tasks and working conditions, a particular set of methods is used during the lesson.

Within the educational system, interactive technologies are implemented depending on the purpose of the lesson and the form of organisation of students' learning activities [14, 33]. Accordingly, there are four groups of interactive technologies:

- interactive technologies of cooperative learning;
- interactive technologies of collective group learning;
- situational modelling technologies;
- technologies for processing discussion issues.

Cooperative learning is a form of organising learning in small groups of students united by a common learning goal that cannot be achieved by a single person in a certain period of time. The common learning goal is achieved in the course of collective learning of each member of the group, provided that each member systematically participates in the learning of all. In this type of learning organisation, the teacher manages the student's work indirectly, through group assignments. Each student has the opportunity to cooperate with all members of the group and work together to achieve the target [7, 58]. Learners need to realise that an individual cannot be successful unless everyone is successful. Each member of the group is responsible for completing his or her part of the task, and the group is responsible for achieving the common purpose. Co-operative learning enables learners to acquire such professionally important clarity as individual competence.

In the initial phase of engaging learners in cooperative learning, it is best to use a form of work in pairs. Working in pairs gives students time to think, exchange ideas, and prepare to speak in front of a group. This form of learning helps to develop communication skills, the ability to express oneself, think critically, persuade and debate. Using this type of collaboration makes it impossible to avoid completing a task [16, 105]. Working in pairs can be useful for learning, consolidation, testing, etc.

A more complex form of group work is a joint project. To develop the project, each group receives a separate task that covers the problem from different angles. This form of work can be used when studying new material that contains a lot of new and diverse information that needs to be found from different sources. The number of working groups and the scope of the assignment depends on the number of students in the training group. In the course of their work, each group uses different sources of knowledge: textbooks, tables, diagrams, and additional literature. During the preparation of the project, each group member reports the results of their research to the entire team, so that everyone becomes aware of a number of issues. Upon completion of the work, each group reports, and the report should contain not

only brief information on the topic but also a proposal. As a result, the proposals of the group representatives are used to create a joint project, which is reviewed and supplemented by a group of experts.

Another method of working in small groups is team information search, which is used to expand and deepen previously acquired knowledge. The instructor develops questions for the groups, the answers to which can be found in various sources of information, sets time for searching and analysing the information, and then listens to the reports from each group. These reports are then repeated and possibly expanded upon by the whole group.

The technology of team-based learning involves the simultaneous joint work of the entire group. Its purpose is to explain certain provisions, motivate cognitive activity, draw attention to problematic issues, update basic knowledge, etc. The teacher encourages the whole group to discuss, and at the end of the lesson, he/she can express his/her opinion. It is not recommended to hold discussions very often and for a long time, as students get tired and become inattentive [11, 8].

A variation of collective discussion is the microphone technology, which allows everyone to say something quickly, in turn, answering questions or expressing their opinion or position. There is no need to comment or evaluate the answers.

The incomplete sentence technique allows you to work on the form of expressing your own ideas, compare them with others, and practice the ability to speak briefly but to the point. This technique can be used in conjunction with the "microphone". The teacher formulates the beginning of a sentence and invites students to speak to complete the thought. In doing so, avoid phrases in the form of questions that can be answered briefly ("yes" or "no").

Brainstorming is a well-known interactive technology of collective discussion used to develop several solutions to a specific problem and encourages participants to take initiative and creativity, allowing them to express their thoughts freely. The purpose of the session, which is held for a limited time, is to collect as many ideas as possible, even fantasies. All ideas and suggestions are written down on the board without discussion or criticism: it is allowed to change or combine ideas, and the expansion of ideas already proposed is encouraged. This promotes the emergence of new, better ideas, and gradually quantity turns into quality. When there are no more new proposals, the whole group starts discussing the proposed ideas and evaluates them [17, 12].

Situational learning technology is a modelling of an event, phenomenon, or performance of certain roles; students are given maximum freedom of intellectual activity, which is limited only by the rules of the game.

Imitation or simulation is the creation of situations in which students copy, in a simplified form, procedures related to the activities of public institutions in real economic, political and cultural life. These are role-playing games in which the sequence of each step and the rules of procedure are clearly defined, and they are miniature versions of reality. These include court, parliamentary, public hearings, meetings, commission meetings, and debates. The purpose of the simulation is to illustrate certain phenomena and decision-making mechanisms, which allows students to dive deep into the problem and understand it from the inside. To do this, the training group is divided into subgroups, each of which is assigned a specific task. The subgroup elects a leader who is responsible for distributing questions among the subgroup members and reporting to the entire study group on the decisions made. Students from other subgroups can ask questions or add to the answers. The rules of preparation and answers are clearly established. The results of the presentations are recorded in a workbook in the form of a summary table. In the next class, the composition of the subgroups may not be changed, but the students receive different tasks, i.e. change their "speciality" [10, 35].

Public hearings are a form of role-playing in which participants gain practical experience in identifying and explaining ideas, interests and values related to the subject matter of the hearing. The purpose of public hearings is to obtain information that will be used to make laws or decisions that affect the interests of the population.

Technology for processing discussion issues. Discussion is an important means of cognitive activity for students in the learning process; it greatly contributes to the development of critical thinking, allows them to define their own position, develops skills in defending their own opinion, and deepens their knowledge of the issue under discussion. Discussion can be used as a method of consolidating learning material and stimulating students' cognitive activity by including a discussion component in certain topics of the class at the stages of checking homework and consolidating the material just learned. The press method is used when discussing controversial issues to develop students' ability to define their position and argue it briefly and convincingly.

A talk show discussion is a conversation technique that involves all students in a group. The tutor can control the course of the discussion and evaluate the participation of each student. The purpose of the discussion is to develop students' public speaking and debating skills, to express and defend their own position, and to develop social and personal activism [5, 34]. The role of a talk show host is played by the faculty member who announces the topic of discussion, offers a short message or video clip about the issue, then invites "invited experts" to speak on the topic and gives the floor to the audience to express their opinions or ask questions of the show participants. Answers should also be short and to the point. Guests can ask each other questions. The host can also ask questions or stop the speaker due to lack of time. The results of the discussion are summed up in terms of content and form.

Conclusions

Intensive social development of a country is impossible without the development of the creative and moral potential of its citizens, without their activity, initiative, and abilities. As is well known, these and other qualities are formed during the period of study, so the most important task of an educational institution is to form the personality of students, to create conditions that ensure the development of their individuality and creative abilities. Students need to be interested in learning, and then learning will become a need for them. English classes should be diverse in content, structure and methods of organising learning activities.

The question of how to teach and learn, how to teach and learn, so that the learning process is as effective as possible, remains relevant for researchers and academic staff. The purpose of further research is to find innovative methods of teaching activities that can help students to think critically, solve complex problems by analysing circumstances and relevant information, weigh and take into account alternative opinions, make informed decisions, discuss, and communicate with other people.

Список використаних джерел

1. Абрамова О.В., Онуфрак О.В. Проектування освітнього процесу технологічної підготовки старшокласників засобами індивідуалізації. Наукові записки. Серія: Педагогічні науки. 2019. Випуск 183. С. 50-54.
2. Беленька Г.В. Інтерактивні методи навчання як засіб розвитку критичного мислення студентів. Актуальні проблеми психології: зб. наук. праць Інституту психології ім. Г.С. Костюка НАПН України. Харків. КЦ ФОП Іванової М.А., 2020. Т.IV. Вип. 16. С. 33-46. URL https://elibrary.kubg.edu.ua/id/eprint/32666/1/H_Bielenka_IMNuaZRKMS_2020.pdf.
3. Гевко І.В. Використання інтерактивних технологій в освіті. Наукові записки. Збірник наукових праць Українського державного університету ім. М.

- Драгоманова. 2018. Вип. 139. С. 53-60. URL: <https://enpuir.npu.edu.ua/handle/123456789/24374>.
4. Гін А. Безкровна атака: Технологія проведення навчального мозкового штурму: Цікава і проста форма навчальної діяльності. 2010. № 8. С. 7–11.
 5. Гур'янова О. Застосування інтерактивних технологій навчання при викладанні харчових технологій для студентів напрямку «професійна освіта». Наукові записки. Серія: Проблеми методики фізико-математичної і технологічної освіти. 2015. Вип. 8. Ч. IV. С. 32-39.
 6. Єрмоленко А. Інтерактивні технології навчання: електронний навчальний курс. Біла Церква: БІНПО, 2022. 37 с.
 7. Зубар Н. М. Застосування інтерактивних методів при вивченні дисципліни «Основи фізіології харчування» // Методичний збірник КУТЕП. 2017. Вип. 2. С. 56–61.
 8. Інтерактивні технології навчання: теорія, практика, досвід : [метод. посіб.] / [авт. укл.: О. Пометун, Л. Пироженко]. Київ : АПН, 2020. 136 с.
 9. Казачінер О.С. Використання нових інформаційних технологій у навчальному процесі. Англійська мова та література. 2015. № 33. С. 5.
 10. Копил І.П. До проблеми застосування сучасних інформаційних технологій при вивченні іноземних мов. Збірник наукових праць. Київ: КНЛУ. 2015. Вип.28. С.30–38.
 11. Крамаренко С.Г. Інтерактивні техніки навчання як засіб розвитку творчого потенціалу учнів. Відкритий урок. 2002. № 5-6. С. 7–10.
 12. Паніна Т. С., Вавілова Л. Н. Сучасні способи активізації навчання. Видавництво "Академія". Харків, 2019. С. 176.
 13. Пометун О. Як оцінити діяльність учнів на інтерактивному уроці. Доба. 2002. № 2. С. 2–6.
 14. Пометун О., Пироженко Л. Сучасний урок. Інтерактивні технології навчання. Київ, 2004. 192 с.
 15. Пометун О.І., Пироженко Л.В. Інтерактивні технології навчання: теорія, практика, досвід / Київ, 2002. 237 с.
 16. Сисоєва С.О. Інтерактивні технології навчання дорослих: навчальнометодичний посібник / НАПН України, Ін-т педагогічної освіти і освіти дорослих. Київ: ВД «ЕКМО», 2011. 324 с.
 17. Ситнік Т. І. Місце й роль інтерактивного навчання у системі інноваційних технологій в закладах вищої освіти. Вісник Черкаського національного університету ім. Б. Хмельницького, Серія: «Педагогічні науки», 2021 (4), 11–18.
 18. Шклярук Г.О. Інтенсифікація навчання іноземної мови з використанням інтерактивних технологій. Англійська мова та література. 2011. № 22. С. 2–3.
 19. Kolb's Learning Cycle. Structural Learning. Advancing Metacognitive Classroom Practice. URL: <https://www.structural-learning.com/post/kolbs-learning-cycle> (date of access: 05.05.2023).